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Research Article

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE DURATION OF DELIVERY: A DELIVERY IS WATER AND NORNAL DELIVERY**Waqar Butt, Kaleem Ifthar, Muhammad Ibtissam Akram**
Services Institute of Medical Sciences Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: To study the nature of normal way of delivery, as a delivery in water without encroaches, in reducing pain and delivery time of delivery.

Methodology: in this research work we study the deferent groups of pregnant womens at the gestational age of 38-42 weeks, the pregnant patient referred to Mayo Hospital Lahore. The one hundred pregnant women equally divided in two groups one is normal delivery and second one is delivery in water. K-square, Kruskal-wiallis, and mann Whitney method is used to find out the pain score and duration of delivery.

Results: According to our research it indicates that the average duration of active delivery was 3.10 hours $\pm$ 0.80 in the delivery in water group, apparently the active phase of delivery in delivery in water is lower than other delivery that is, 4.70 hours $\pm$ 0.80 (0.050>p). the second circumstanced of delivery was 0.530 hours $\pm$ 0.220 in the delivery in water group, apparently lower than that of the other group of delivery, that is, 0.88 hrs $\pm$ 0.43 (0.050>p). On the bases of above theory amount of pain and duration of delivery was decrease In delivery in water which is 3.530 $\pm$ 0.790 (p<0.05) as compare to other groups of delivery which is 6.90 $\pm$ 1.70.

Conclusion: The above result shows that delivery in water may be a suitable, nonmedical, and nonaggressive choice, because it reduces the pain and duration of delivery.

Key Words: Delivery in water, Normal delivery, Pain; Duration of delivery.

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INTRODUCTION:

For a pain relief in pregnant women's during delivery the gynecologist mostly used pain killer and sedatives as a medicine. The delivery pain did not control by the help of medicine because it is considering one of the demanding from of pain all over in the world pregnant women's want to go through normal way of delivery otherwise her accept to face with caesarian broth. The American association of gynecologists attempt to decrease caesarian broth in pregnant women's due to this effort it reduces the rate of caesarian from 25.5% to 15.5% during the 2017-2018 now a day the caesarian delivery is increases in Pakistan. Ministry of health survey on caesarian section the figure shows that the rate of caesarian to be 3 times higher than world to reduce pain sensation in patient entonox capsules of nitrous oxide and Epidural or spinal anesthesia; and some other pain killer are used as a medicine. There are many countries in the world which used Nonaggressive and nonmedical method during delivery in water which increases the ambit of pain in pregnant women and produces effective uterine contractions, resulting in a more easily tolerated process of delivery.

Our nine-year continue study on 9518 deliveries cases in these deliveries the 3617 deliveries in water and 5901 is normal deliveries it the end we conclude that the safest way for both mother and child is delivery in water. On the other hand, we compared 220 deliveries with delivery in water it the end result show that delivery in water is helpful for long and difficult pregnancies. A study in Tehran on 100 women's that has not given birth divided in 2 control and case groups, indicated that the need for medical interference, using oxytocin, analgesic, and episiotomy was lower in the case group. We carried out this study to compare the duration and pain of delivery between delivery in water and normal delivery in Mayo Hospital Lahore

METHODOLOGY:

This is an experimental effort which is done in Mayo Hospital Lahore, from February 2017 to February 2018. The 100 cases of pregnant women's these cases uniformly divided in two groups 1st delivery in water and 2nd normal delivery. The common condition between two groups consistency, age, and gestational age. All The pregnant women's under the age of 16-28 years old, 1-2 are pregnant and gestational age of 38-42 weeks. For all patients a questionnaire was filled out by teammate of the research, including the following questions: Age; gestational age; pregnancy; and also studied the duration of delivery in both phases; count of pain; amount of ambit analgesics and used of oxytocin; need for episiotomy; to study

the Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity and respiration (APGAR score) of newborn baby; and patient's satisfaction with the delivery mode.

If pregnant women accept written application from hospital to undergo delivery in water; during the active phase of delivery than women enter to the warm pool; and throughout the delivery recorded all process like the fetal heart rate, pain score, and amount of analgesics and oxytocin. On the other hand, if the patients need for caesarian, such a patient would be remove from the study lest. Normally delivery develops in two hours if the duration of delivery increase from two hours, then oxytocin injection is used to relieve the vaginal contractions. If the pregnant woman needed analgesics, she would be administered promethazine and the number of utilization would be noted distinctly. The visual analog score count is used to find out the delivery pain; scoring from 0 to 10. All the quantitative variables were shown as average and standard deviation, and then they were analyzed using SPSS software and tests of variation analysis, Chi-square, Kruskal-Wallis, and Mann Whitney were conducted. P values of lower than 0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS:

The total count of patients was 100 uniformly distributed in 2 groups 1st normal delivery and 2nd delivery in water. The two groups further distributed in 2 subdivisions first one is nulliparous and second one is pregnant women. The 1st nulliparous subdivision of delivery in water the medium age of pregnant women was 20 ± 2.10 years, the 2nd young pregnant subdivision of delivery in water group age was 25 ± 2.10 years, all the pregnant women with the sublime average of 21 ± 2.50 years are delivery in water group. The 1st nulliparous subdivision of normal delivery group pregnant women was 19.8 ± 2.40 years old the 2nd young pregnant subdivision of normal delivery group was 21 ± 2.30 years old, all the pregnant women in the normal delivery group with the sublime average of 20 ± 2.50 years old.

In this research we also study the deferent gestational age of the pregnant women the result was shown that 36 percent of cases at 38-39 weeks, and 33 percent at 39-40 weeks, and 26 percent at 40-41 weeks, and 5 percent at 41-42 weeks of gestational age (Table 1st). The nulliparous subdivision of delivery in water group the average duration of the active phase was 3.60 ± 0.820 hours. In the 2nd young pregnant subdivision of delivery in water group the duration is 2.80 ± 0.80 hours. For delivery in water patient the total average duration of the active phase was 4.70 ± 0.80 hours.

Table-1st: Distribution of relative frequency of pregnant women on the basis of delivery mode and need for Oxytocin

Groups	Oxytocin		Total
	Yes	No	
W percentage	16.30	83.70	100.00
L percentage	56.90	43.10	100.00
Total percentage	37.00	63.00	100.00

P<0.001

L: delivery in Land W: delivery in Water

For the nulliparous subdivision of normal delivery patient, the average period of the active phase was 5.20 ± 0.50 hours. And in the 2nd young pregnant subdivision of normal delivery patient average delivery period of active phase was 4.320 ± 0.80 hours. For the normal delivery team of women, the total average of the active phase was 4.70 ± 0.80 hours. For the nulliparous subdivision of delivery in water patient the average period of the 2nd phase of delivery was 0.620 ± 0.210 hours, and for the 2nd young pregnant sub of division delivery in water patients' average period was 0.340 ± 0.80 hours. For delivery in water team of pregnant women the total average of the 2nd phase of delivery was 0.53 ± 0.22 hours. For normal delivery patients the average of the 2nd phase of delivery was 0.880 ± 0.430 hours; therefore, the

decrease in the active and 2nd phases of delivery in water was numerically significant in relationship with the normal delivery patients ($0.05 > p$).

When the delivery of a patient did not occur in the active phase then the patients were conduct oxytocin, the used of oxytocin amount for both team of patients was recorded. The research shows that water delivery patients were 83.70 percent, and the normal delivery patients were 43.10 percent and due to this reason the need of oxytocin is decrease. The reduction in need for oxytocin with delivery in water is considerable in comparison with normal delivery group ($0.05 > p$) (Table-1st). Delivery in water & normal delivery

Table-2nd: Distribution of relative frequency of pregnant women on the basis of delivery mode and need for painkillers

Groups	Analgesic		Total
	Yes	No	
W percentage	14.30	85.70	100.00
L percentage	58.80	41.20	100.00
Total percentage	37.00	63.00	100.00

0.0010>p

W: delivery in Water L: delivery in Land

The quantity of analgesics (promethazine in this study) used for both patients was recorded. The research of our study show that the delivery in water patients were 85.70 percent and normal delivery patients were 41.20 percent which did not need analgesics. The decrease in need for analgesics with delivery in water is considerable in comparison with normal delivery patients ($0.05 > p$) (Table-2nd). The visible analog scale (0-10) is used to determining amount of pain score in pregnant women. In this method, the intensity of pain is scored based on the patient's awareness of pain from 0-10. From our study we declare that the average pain score for water delivery patients is not exceeded from 3.530 ± 0.790 . On the other hand, in normal delivery cases the pain score is

exceeded up to 6.960 ± 1.70 . which shows that in normal delivery cases the patient faced with more pain than delivery in water because the visible analog score shows more deviation in normal delivery ($p < 0.05$) (Table-3rd).

From our research it is cleared that the delivery in water patients was 61.00 percent which did not need episiotomy, as compare to normal delivery patients were 35.60 percent need it. The above study about the use of episiotomy in both groups declare that for normal delivery case we need episiotomy as compare to delivery in water groups because p is greater than 0.05 (Table-4th). Such newborns babe which Apgars score is less than 8 during delivery in water did not leave a babe in water more than 5 minutes; 85.70

percent of these women had Apgar score 10, and 14.30 percent patient had Apgar score under 8-10. 54.10 percent of women in the normal delivery case had Apgar score up to 10, 31.30 percent delivery patients had Apgar score under 8-10, and 14.60 percent patients had Apgar score under 6-8, and such new-

borns babe needed Neonatal, Intensive Care Unit. Later we also studied patient's satisfaction about the delivery mode. About 72.39 percent of patients declared that they will absolutely choose this mode for their next pregnancy.

Apgar scoring system				
Indicator		0 points	1 points	2 points
A	Activity	Absent	Flexed limbs	Active
P	Pulse	Absent	<100 BPM	>100BPM
G	Grimace	Floppy	Mini response to stimulation	Promot response to stimulation
A	Appearance	Blue pale	Pink body Blue extremities	Pink
R	Respiration	Absent	Slow and irregular	Vigorous cry

Table-3rd: Average pain score in pregnant

Women considering delivery mode			
Groups	Pain		
	N	Mean	Standard deviation
delivery in Water	50.00	3.530	0.790
delivery in Water	50.00	6.960	1.70
Total	100.00	5.280	2.170

0.001>p

21.30 percent patient agreed that they may prefer it for the next pregnancy, and 6.40 percent accepted caesarian because they will naturally not prefer delivery in water for their next pregnancy. 8.70 percent of women in the normal delivery patient said that they will naturally accept delivery in water for their next pregnancy, 39.10 percent of patients accepted that they select delivery in water for their next pregnancy, and according to our research 52.20 percent of patients will not become pregnant again, or otherwise will accept caesarian as the alternative for delivery. in both groups 13 patients needed caesarian delivery due to this reason we removed such patients from our research.

DISCUSSION:

The effect of our research in Mayo Hospital describe that the period of the 1st and 2nd groups of delivery, normal delivery taken more time than delivery in water group because of hot water touching the nipples and stimulation oxytocin discharge, and decrease vaginal contractions in patients. Also, due to the used of water as a sitting medium for delivery the hydrostatic (fluid exerted pressure on immersed body) ef-

fect of water increase contraction pressure in womb and rehabilitate the parentage of the presenting part. On the other hand, Cluette et al. initiated that in case of non-developing deliveries and dystopia the alternative for this case is delivery in water, with the purpose of decreasing medical interference like administering oxytocin.

In 1 research 150 women is divided in two groups 1st group of 70 women undergoing delivery in water and 2nd group of 70 women undergoing normal delivery our research did not indicate any deference between the two phase of delivery. On the other hand, the duration of the 2nd phase of delivery was noted that normal delivery taken 9 minutes less time than delivery in water because the patient leaves in hot water for same extant due to the hydro analgesic effect of hot water that relaxes the vaginal contractions but hot water does not affect the delivery process. In delivery in water process the reduction is noted in pain score and in the need of episiotomy because the hot water relaxes the vaginal contraction. in both process the respiration and Apgar are recorded equal in newborn babe.

Table-4th: Division of frequency of pregnant women on the basis of delivery mode and need for episiotomy

Groups	Episiotomy		Total
	Yes	No	
W percentage	38.80	61.20	100.00
L percentage	64.40	35.60	100.00
Total percentage	51.10	48.90	100.00

P<0.001

W: delivery in Water

L: delivery in Land

One research on 220 deliveries in water conducted in 20018 by the result of that study delivery in water is beneficial for groups of hard delivery and assists the process. Our research shows that in normal delivery pain score and the amount of analgesic needed are considerably higher than delivery in water: 41.2 percent of those patients which is in the category of normal delivery and 85.70 percent of those patients which undergoing delivery in water did not need any medicine for pain relief (analgesics). Geissbuehler et al. 2018 reported that if the deliveries in water were 69.70 percent and normal deliveries were 58 percent it did not need analgesics. Our research in Mayo Hospital shows that deliveries in water were 83.7 percent and normal deliveries were 43.1 percent which did not need oxytocin injection during delivery. Bourke et al reported that oxytocin injection is required for those patient who given delivery in water and 98 percent of women mentioned that delivery in water is comfortable for deliveries.

In our research, deliveries in water were 61.00 percent and normal deliveries were 35.60 percent did not required episiotomy which indicates a consequential consideration. Comparing with other researches, we also study many cases of episiotomy during our research, apparently due to our caution to prevent 3rd and 4th grade laceration. More we study on two thousand deliveries notifies a considerable decrease in episiotomy, pain and also control blood loss with delivery in water. More in this study mother's compensation and 5 and 10 minute apgars (Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity, and Respiration) of newborn were consequentially higher.

During our study we noted that Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity, and Respiration case did not lower than 8 or otherwise we required Neonatal, Intensive Care Unit with delivery in water. Whereas in normal delivery case, 14.6% of newborns had Apgar (Appearance, Pulse, Grimace, Activity, and Respiration) 6-8, in this type of case we needed Neonatal, Intensive Care Unit, and otherwise the death ratio is increase in newborn child. Also one study recently in

March, during delivery in water did not observed any case of aspiration or perinatal complications and they expected this mode of delivery is safest way for both mother and newborn child.

Grunebaum et al. concluded that Neonatal, Intensive Care Unit required for 6.490 percent of child born in water and 0.50 percent of child born normal. Joanne et al. conclude from his study that in normal delivery, the premature babe acidosis increases and the partial pressure of carbon dioxide of umbilical artery is considerably higher than delivery in water.12 Kwee et al. reported that delivery in water the water hydrostatic pressure increases enhances placental uterine circulation and central blood volume, leading to battering fetal environment and holding fetal distress.

Johnson et al. reported that with delivery in water, delinquent to the assume temperature of water, absence of voice, touch, etc. catalyst, the effect of gravitational force on the neonate is smaller, and perfection of basic cord the newborn babe will not start breathing and thus child will not aspirate water before emerging from the water. A Biochemistry and Molecular Genetics report predict that delivery in water is safe full for both mother and child only one risk of water aspiration in newborn otherwise it 95 percent safe and good, the main problem of delivery in water is perfection of basic cord before taking the newborn babe out of water.

CONCLUSION

Delivery in water is alternative for normal delivery because it decreases the duration of delivery, patient's pain, medical intervention such as administering analgesics, oxytocin injection and episiotomy, and also absence of harmful effect on the newborn babe. If delivery in water is done under the close observation of mother and child, then it is considerable help full and good for both. Our studied on the patients' satisfaction at the end we conclude that the patient desire to experience this mode of delivery again for their next pregnancies, by the help of delivery in water we control the ratio of C-section, a

measure in line with health of women during pregnancy which promotes natural delivery. We recommend the pregnant women to follow delivery in water if the health center providing the necessary equipment and educating health personnel, and also increasing the mind of pregnant women about the advantages of delivery in water.

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